

Conference Abstract

New data on two species of the genus *Hemicycliophora* de Man, 1921 (Tylenchida)

Zhenya Ivanova Ilieva[‡], Iliyan Lazarov Iliev[§]

[‡] Institute of Soil Science, Agrotechnology and Plant Protection, Sofia, Bulgaria

[§] Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski", Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Zhenya Ivanova Ilieva (zhenya107a@gmail.com)

Received: 24 Sep 2019 | Published: 27 Sep 2019

Citation: Ilieva ZI, Iliev IL (2019) New data on two species of the genus *Hemicycliophora* de Man, 1921 (Tylenchida).

ARPHA Conference Abstracts 2: e46808. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.2.e46808>

Abstract

Species of the genus *Hemicycliophora* de Man, 1921 are not very often reported from natural or agricultural areas of Bulgaria. *Hemicycliophora labiata* Colbran 1920 was reported from the region of Blagoevgrad (Choleva-Abadjieva and Budurova 1983) but in later studies no other records of the genus were found. We isolated specimens of *Hemicycliophora* from intensively irrigated patches with wilt and postponed plants from a strawberry field in the Plovdiv region (30.10.2015) and a golf course in the Dobrich region (27.07.2019). Nematodes were isolated by Oostenbrink elutriator followed by 72 h exposition, killed by gently heating at temperature of 55°C and fixed in FAA. Fifty two specimens from Plovdiv region and 31 specimens from Dobrich were mounted in glycerol after Seinhorst (1959).

The specimens from Plovdiv were identified as *H. poranga* Monteiro & Lordello, 1978. Their morphology is similar to those of the population described from Pistachino, Italy (Subbotin et al. 2017). According to our knowledge this is the first record of the species on the Balkans.

The population from Dobrich was similar morphologically to Polish populations of *H. epicharoides* Loof, 1968 (Brzeski 1998). It differed by a longer vulvar sleeve in some of the specimens and a generally less stout tail. That is first record of the species in Bulgaria, but

it was found on the Balkans in Serbia and Greece (Krnjaic and Krnjaic 1976, Subbotin et al. 2017). Morphometrics and microphotograph for both species were obtained.

Keywords

Hemicyclophora, poranga, epicharoides, strawberry, golf course, morphology

Presenting author

Zhenya Ilieva

Presented at

Vth International Congress on Biodiversity: „Taxonomy, Speciation and Euro-Mediterranean Biodiversity“

References

- Brzeski M (1998) Nematodes of Tylenchida in Poland and temperate Europe. 1. Muzeum i Instytutu Zoologii, Polska Akademia Nauk (MiZ PAN), Warszawa, 397 pp. [In English]. [ISBN 8385192840]
- Choleva-Abadjieva B, Budurova L (1983) Nematodes Parasitizing on Black Currant (*Ribes nigrum* var. *europium* L.) in Bulgaria. Acta Zoologica Bulgarica 21: 67-77. [In Bulgarian (English summary)].
- Krnjaic D, Krnjaic S (1976) Distribution of nematodes in clumps of *Festuca vaginata*. Nematologia Mediterranea 4: 161-170. [In English]. URL: <https://journals.flvc.org/nemamedia/article/view/85211>
- Seinhorst JW (1959) A rapid method for the transfer of nematodes from fixative to anhydrous glycerine. Nematologica 4: 67-69. [In English]. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/187529259X00381>
- Subbotin S, Chitambar J, Chizhov V, Stanley J, Inserra R, Doucet M, McClure M, Ye W, Yeates GW, Mollov D, Cantalapiedra-Navarrete C, Vovlas N, Berg Evd, Castillo P (2017) Molecular phylogeny, diagnostics, and diversity of plant-parasitic nematodes of the genus *Hemicyclophora* (Nematoda: Hemicyclophoridae). Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society 171: 475-506. [In English]. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zoj.12145>